

Research

Optical Performance Characteristics Evaluation of 3M Optical Thin Film Structure with Enhancing Incident Angle of Light and Refractive Indices of Growth Materials

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Abstract: We report on the evaluation of optical characteristics of three media (3M) optical thin films due to enhancement of refractive indices of growth material and incident angle of light to the air-film interface by theoretical analysis and then simulation using Matlab. It has been found that optical performance characteristics, transmittance and reflectance as a function of wavelength of 3M film structure are noticeably influenced with increasing incident angle of light at the air-film interface, and refractive indices of film material and substrate. In particular, frequency or periodicity of reflected spectra is found to have distinct values with increasing incident angle from 5 to 40 degree while the device is in operation. Opposite tendency is observed in transmitted spectra. The dissimilar refractive indices of film affect moderately on the reflectance and transmittance of optical thin film. On the other hand, the reflectance decreases significantly, and oppositely transmittance improves drastically with increasing refractive index of substrate. The proposed research work in this study would be very helpful to develop nano-coating technology to determine best film-substrate materials having desired refractive indices, at a specified incident angle of light for particular application in the third-generation optical devices.

Keywords: 3M (Three Media) Optical Thin film, Substrate, Transmittance, Reflectance, Angle of Incidence, Optical Properties.

Introduction

Recently, the research on optical thin film has attracted much more attention to the researcher due to it's many potential applications in the third generation optical devices such as window layers

in solar cells, field emitters, ultraviolet laser emission, photodetectors, piezoelectricity, biosensors, light emitting diode and information technology etc.¹⁻⁶ Thin films are important because they offer the potential for low-cost processing with minimal material usage while fulfilling application requirements.⁷ Optical and radiated properties are fundamental physical properties that describe the interaction between electromagnetic waves and matter from deep ultraviolet to far-infrared spectral regions.⁸ In fact, optical property measurements and analysis are usually the preferred valuable methods for measuring thin film characteristics because they are accurate, nondestructive and require little or no sample preparation.⁹

Effect of thickness on the optical properties of optical thin films was studied previously.^{10,11} We previously reported that the amplitude and periodicity of the reflectance and transmittance spectra are greatly influenced by the different film materials and substrates.¹² Brongersma *et al.* previously reported on light management for high-performance photovoltaic cells by using high refractive index nanostructures.⁷ However, the refractive index of film media determines not only the phase velocity of light, but also refraction, reflection and diffraction occurring at the boundary of the medium.¹³ Therefore, this parameter plays a vital role specially in optical thin film to be applied for specific application. Unfortunately, the availability of materials with suitable refractive indices is very limited, particularly for optical films.¹³ In addition, the efficient positioning of thin film device with respect to the incident light during operation is important¹⁴ because the incident angle of light at the air-film interface has the significant effect on the optical performance, reflectance and transmittance of the thin film. Therefore, it is of great important to extensive study, analyze and evaluate optical performance characteristics of 3M optical thin film structure with enhancing refractive indices of growth materials and incident angle of light. This research work would help us to determine desirable optical thin film with improved performance for particular application, and eventually develop the nano-coating technology for the next generation optical devices.

In this research paper, the film thickness, roughness, surface morphology were considered as constant whereas the reflectance-transmittance characteristics of optical thin-film have been analyzed, visualized and evaluated for different angle of incident light at the air-film interface and for various refractive indices of film- and substrate separately.

Theoretical Analysis and Matlab Simulation

The schematic diagram of the 3M Optical thin-film structure with reflection and transmission of incident light is shown in Figure 1. As can be seen from this figure, light whenever incidents on the air-film interface having different refractive indices at a specified angle, the fraction of light is reflected from the surface while some other amount of electromagnetic wave is refracted through the surface and finally transmitted. In this study, the refractive index of the transparent input medium (air), n_0 is real. However, the film has optical losses so that its refractive index is complex and dispersive such that $\bar{n}_f(\lambda) = n_f(\lambda) - ik_f(\lambda)$ with the real refractive index, $n_f(\lambda)$ and absorptive index, $k_f(\lambda)$ and, being functions of the light wavelength.

Figure 1: Reflection and transmission of incident light in the 3M Optical thin-film structure

Depending on application of the thin-film structure, its substrate is produced from different materials including transparent dielectrics or semiconductors. Thus, in general, the refractive index of substrate also has the complex form, $\bar{n}_s(\lambda) = n_s(\lambda) - ik_s(\lambda)$. Some assumptions have been made in this analysis. We considered film as slightly absorbing material ($k_f^2 \ll n_f^2$) on a transparent substrate ($k_s = 0$). Consequently, the assumption yields $\bar{n}_f(\lambda) \cong n_f(\lambda)$ and $\bar{n}_s(\lambda) \cong n_s(\lambda)$. Under this condition, we calculated total transmitted and reflected light using the Figure 1, and thereafter obtained the reflectance and transmittance of the 3M thin-film in terms of incident angle of electromagnetic spectrum and refractive indices of film- and substrate as shown in following equations (1) and (2) respectively.

$$R_{eff} = \frac{x^2 + y^2 + 2xy \cos z}{1 + x^2 y^2 + 2xy \cos z} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$T_{eff} = \frac{16n_0^2 n_f^2 n_s}{1+x^2 y^2 + 2xy \cos z} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

where $x = \frac{n_0 - n_f}{n_0 + n_f}$, $y = \frac{n_f - n_s}{n_f + n_s}$, $\delta = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_f d_f \cos \theta_i$, and $z = 2\delta$, d_f represents the film thickness, λ is the wavelength of visible light and θ_i is the incident angle of light to the air-film interface. The above two equations (1) and (2) have been simulated by Matlab code to visualize- and evaluate transmittance and reflectance spectra of this structure for different incident angle of light and refractive indices of film- and substrate.

Results and Discussions

R_{eff} and T_{eff} spectra as a function of wavelength have been visualized in Figure 2 for different θ_i 5°, 30° and 40°.

Figure 2: Reflectance and Transmittance spectra for different incident angle of light

As can be seen from this figure that the periodicity of oscillation in both spectra dramatically affected by incident angle of light. The oscillations are caused by the reflected wave interference in the thin film. Periods of these oscillations differs from each other. The lowest reflection of 4% and the highest reflection of 27.5% of the incident light have been occurred at different wavelengths for the different incident angles of light. The lowermost and the uppermost reflection were transpired at 350 nm and 700 nm respectively whenever the light is incident at 30° to the air-film interface. Unlikely, at the incident angles 5° and 40°, oscillations have been observed on both

spectra. As the incident angle changed from 5° to 40° , the number of oscillations of the transmittance and reflectance spectra increased. The maximum reflectance and minimum transmittance happened at 420 nm for 5° while at 420 nm, 580 nm for 40° . However, the minimum percentage reflectance and maximum percentage transmittance obtained at 625 nm for 5° while at 370 nm, 480 nm for 40° . Thus, the reflectance and transmittance characteristics of the thin film are powerfully dependent on the incident angle of light.

Figure 3: Reflectance and Transmittance spectra for different refractive index of film

Figure 3 shows R_{eff} and T_{eff} spectra as a function of wavelength for different n_f , 2.21, 2.3 and 2.46. In this case, the angle of incident is kept constant at 30° and the film material is considered as slightly absorbing layer. It has been noticed from this figure that around 5% least reflectance occurred nearly at 350 nm for 2.21, 2.3 and 2.46 film index while peak transmittance is around 95% at the same wavelength. After 350 nm, the reflectance of thin film increases with increasing wavelength of light. At 505 nm, the amount reflectance is same as 22.5% for all films while transmittance is 77.5%. The maximum reflections done by the thin film at 700 nm are 28%, 31% and 35% for 2.21, 2.3 and 2.46 respectively. At the same time, the lowest 28%, 31% and 35% transmittance occurred at 700 nm for film index 2.21, 2.3 and 2.46 respectively. This evaluation give us the way that the required R_{eff} and T_{eff} of the thin film can be obtained by selecting suitable film material having desired refractive index.

The special effects of substrate on the optical thin film have been evaluated by visualizing the R_{eff} and T_{eff} spectra as shown in Figure 4 for different n_s , 1.25, 1.472 and 1.89. The substrate material was considered as transparent layer.

Figure 4: Reflectance and Transmittance Spectra for different refractive index of substrate

The amplitude of oscillation of both spectra were found to be significantly affected by n_s but the periodicity of oscillation was not affected. The maximum and minimum reflectance-transmittance has been happened at some specific wavelengths for various n_s . The highest reflectance viz 33% for 1.25; 27.5% for 1.472 and 19% for 1.89 has been observed at 365 nm and 600 nm wavelengths. However, the lowest reflectance occurring at 450 nm are 2% ,4%, 10% for 1.25, 1.472, 1.89 respectively. At the same time, the highest transmittance 98%, 96%, 90% for 1.25, 1.472, 1.89 respectively have been found at 450 nm wavelength. Thus, substrate's refractive index strongly affected the reflectance and transmittance performance of the thin film.

Conclusion

Optical characteristics of three media (3M) optical thin films has been evaluated in details due to enhancement of refractive indices of growth material and incident angle of light to the air-film interface by theoretical analysis and then simulation using Matlab. Optical performance characteristics of 3M film structure are found to be noticeably influenced with increasing incident angle of light at the air-film interface, and refractive indices of film material and substrate.

Frequency or periodicity of reflected spectra had distinct values at different incident angle from 5 to 40 degree while illuminating by light. Opposite tendency is observed in transmitted spectra. The dissimilar refractive indices of film affect moderately on the reflectance and transmittance of optical thin film. Moreover, the reflectance decreases significantly, and oppositely transmittance improves drastically with increasing refractive index of substrate. The proposed way in this study would be very helpful to develop nano-coating technology to determine best film-substrate materials having desired refractive indices, at a specified incident angle of light for particular application in the third-generation optical devices.

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Dedication

Dedicated to our Parents.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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